

**THE IMPORTANCE OF SOIL SCIENCE IN THE FORMATION OF
ECOLOGICAL CULTURE**

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ABSTRACT: In this article talk about, on the basis of the integration of Sciences in the formation of ecological culture of youth, the implementation of the creative reduction to the solution of today's problems. In the process of coordination and harmonization of interaction and interaction of nature and society with the current period, where the development of Science and technology is accelerated, such environmental problems arise, they are interpreted as the actual problems of our time. Although the main cause of the ecological crisis were natural processes, but they arose under the influence of anthropogen factor-human activity.

KEYWORDS: environmental crisis, evolutionary process, dialectical unit, environmental ignorance, anthropogen factor, natural ecosystem, biosenoses, ecosystem agrobiocenoses, minerals, chemical means.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the process of coordination and harmonization of interaction and interaction of nature and society with the current period, where the development of Science and technology is accelerated, such environmental problems arise, they are interpreted as the actual problems of our time.

Although the main cause of the ecological crisis were natural processes, but they arose under the influence of anthropogen factor-human activity. Due to this, it is useless to evaluate this crisis as a pure natural-historical, evolutionary process or to link it to a lack of water. If this problem is analyzed on the basis of the dialectical unit of social, economic, political and cultural knowledge, an important

aspect of which has not yet been considered is manifested in the will not formation of the necessary environmental knowledge in young people. From this point of view, it would be correct to assess the ecological crisis in our country, first of all, as a tragedy of "environmental ignorance". After all, the lifestyle of any people is a good indicator of environmental knowledge. The acceleration of socio-economic development in the current market conditions, the improvement of the welfare and standard of living of the people largely depends on the effectiveness of agricultural production.

However, due to the lack of environmental knowledge in the majority of young people, local- natural characteristics, laws of conservation in the production process have not been taken into account.

It is almost unthinkable that the rough use of technology and the disruption of technology can have a negative impact on the environment. As a result, agriculture has become a factor that has a strong impact on the environment, which in this case causes ecological crises in the nature of our country: -land area increase, natural ecotism, which arose in the process of long evolutionary development as a result of the slow growth of pet food, is in place of biocenoses artificially created by man appeared ecosystem-agrobiocenoses; -there is a sharp decrease in moisture due to the development of protected lands, the destruction of the taiga, the scientific unreasonable drying of lakes; -incorrect agrotechnical and meliorative treatment of the ground, due to the violation of the natural earth's layer, the composition of soils has changed, productivity decreased, it allowed a decrease in moisture from water bodies, an increase in dust particles in the air; -- failure to comply with the methods and norms of irrigation of crops led to excessive moistening of the fields and secondary salinity, water wastage; -excessive use of mineral fertilizers and chemicals by the norm and non-compliance with the rules of their use caused pollution of the environment with various substances lying on the nature, which caused a violation of the life activity of living beings;

-the construction of many large livestock and poultry facilities has increased the chances of pollution of the environment with industrial waste; --improper use of agricultural machinery and vehicles led to an increase in soil density, a violation of moisture retention and water permeability, pollution of the environment by side oil residues, toxic gases.

-it is possible to positively solve the problems of Environmental Protection at the moment when agricultural production is accompanied by the addition of the following main directions of rational use of nature: -to organize and improve the activities of the agricultural industry sectors taking into account the impact of proaduction on the environment; -productive and economical use of land-water, plant and animal resources, local and chemical fertilizers and side-lubricants; -unrefined of the hereditary richness of the native plant and animal nature, and the protection of ecosystems as a component of the biosphere; -strict consideration of environmental factors and measures for the protection of nature in the conduct of farming and livestock; -carrying out melioration works in accordance with the requirements of nature protection and to expand the area of field quixote trees; -restoration of damaged lands and their use in agriculture due to industrial, transport and road construction; -improve the melioration condition of the slope and natural fodder fields; -transition to low-output and non-output technology in the processing of agricultural products; -reduction of environmental pollution on the basis of improvement of methods of using mineral fertilizers and chemicals; -constant control of soil, water, air quality and condition.

It has become a tradition to organize the collection of "secondary homashyo" in secondary schools. Students actively participated in the collection of waste paper and rags, which allows them to save forest wealth in thousands of hectares, collecting and multiplying valuable medicinal plants, collecting ferrous and non-ferrous metals.

Below, based on our own work experiences, we will acquaint physics personnel with the content of materials on the topics "moisture", "evaporation",

"capillary phenomena". The mass of water vaporizing through the soil depends primarily on the saturation of the layer with water vapor and its capillary properties. The more moist air in the lower layers, and the smaller the soil structure, the faster the evaporation process takes place. Dense soil evaporates more water than softened soil.

Therefore, in order to keep moisture on the ground longer after watering, it is necessary to soften it in time, that is, to cultivate it. Water supply, in particular, irrigation works, in the event that the water is not used sparingly, unpleasant consequences can arise, that is, saline areas. The essence of this phenomenon is that in dry climatic conditions, groundwater contains a large amount salts of sulphate and hydrochloric acid in water. When the crop area is moistened and watered, mineral groundwater sales rise and the salts dissolved in water rise to the top layer of the soil.

When processing the ground, the capillary connection between the top layer and the bottom layer is broken, thereby reducing evaporation.

The speed of evaporation is greatly influenced by the wind, its direction and strength. More winds accelerate evaporation, while wet winds, on the contrary, reduce evaporation. In addition, the amount of water vaporization in the soil affects the crops that are sown, their density and agrotechnics. Water vaporization in the soil depends on the rise of moisture from the lower layer to the upper layer, the relative humidity of the air, the nature of the soil, the speed of the wind and the relief of the Earth. Mineral sizot water, which is located near the surface or Once Upon a time on

the surface in the formation of saline soils and finally, dissolve in all kinds of salts ,salt hogs on the shores of the Sea play the role of the main source vs the fact that they fly in the wind.

The composition of these dissolved salts includes kaltsium chloride, magnesium chloride, magnesium sulfate, osh tuzi, sodium sulfate, sodium carbonate and others.

Dissolved salts in water, in particular, chloride salts, poison plants. In addition, salts raise the osmotic pressure of the soil solution. Thus, the phenomenon of the physiological dryness of the soil occurs. The essence of this phenomenon is that, how to thirst from anhydrous when plants lack moisture in the soil, even if there are a lot of salts in the soil, it is so thirsty from a lack of water. The essence of this phenomenon is that, how to thirst from anhydrous when plants lack moisture in the soil, even if there are a lot of salts in the soil, it is so thirsty from a lack of water.

Methods for washing the brine of saline lands will be different. In all conditions, it is useful to wash the brine in the period when the current soil water saturation is most lowered. When the soil is washed, the Earth softens and quality plows. Depending on the degree of salinity of the soil, before and after plowing the land the brine is washed. Such, weak and moderately saline soils until plowing and the strongly salted ones will give a good result if they are washed after autumn plowing.

The water norms for washing soil brine are determined depending on the degree of salinity of the land, the depth of settling of the soil waters and the mechanical composition of the soil, as well as other characteristics. How much earlier to enter the brine, he gives so much better results. If the brine is washed several times, it is necessary to give water in turn, so that the water absorbs into the ground. To prevent the salinity of the Earth, it is necessary to reduce the evaporation of water.

To reduce water vaporization, that is, as a barrier to the rise of moisture through the capillaries to the surface of the soil, reducing the evaporation surface, installing anti-wind barriers and adjusting the air and soil temperature, it is necessary not to work on lands of poor quality.

Another way to combat the salinity of soils is to plant trees. Cultivated trees, the soil of which is salty, should be drought- and frost-resistant, fast-growing, valuable wood or fruit-bearing and affable trees, capable of bearing. Such trees as

white tulle, Eastern Maple, bagerak, and at the same time from fruit trees such trees as apricots, pears, peaches, plums, chilonzhi, white mulberry withstand the salinity of the Earth.

On the basis of the rapid development of Science and technology, the slowdown in production and, in this regard, the large use of Natural Resources, in turn, led to a violation of the ecological balance.

It is practically observed that the violation of ecological balance in the regions occurs directly as a result of the interaction of natural and anthropogen factors.

Ecological balance is changing at an unprecedented level at a new stage of scientific and technical development at the moment.

The main reason for this is the excessive use of Natural Resources and, as a consequence, their rational and in need, the possibility of destructions, the protection of nature, the scientific solution of problems, the numerous pollution of the atmosphere and water bodies are associated with soil poverty, the ever-decreasing nature and animal world, to nature is associated with the cooling of human affection and the activity of other factors.

The environmental crisis is turning into a terrible reality in our lives, and this is of great concern to the general public day by day.

Therefore, one of the pressing problems of the present time is the education of students with this in-depth environmental education.

During our observations, we were convinced that the Uzbek people's attitude to the land, water, plant and animal worlds, in the process of educational work, remained aside from the use of wonderful narratives and good words formed for thousands of years. After all, our ancestors used the Land-Water Resources for their needs. Especially those who are in a relationship of austerity with respect to water, spit in the water, throw something into it, get dirty, is considered a grave and unforgivable sin. Now the revival of these traditions among our generations, the effective use of them in the educational process depends on the level of

knowledge of the reader and on the extent to which environmental knowledge in his person is contained.

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